

1 Title: Unveiling the Potential of Host Susceptibility Factor Genes: A Novel
2 Approach for Resistance Breeding

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11 Abstract

12 In their co-existence for millennia, plants and pathogens have been co-evolving diverse
13 arrays of biochemical arms against each other for survival. The arms race between
14 them is a complex process demonstrated by the “zig-zag” model. Pathogens with
15 superior virulent arms often cause vast amounts of yield loss and compromise quality
16 and safety in numerous plant species. Plants should be equipped with myriads of
17 resistance genes (R genes) to overcome pathogen-associated losses. However, the use
18 of R genes in the breeding programs is often hindered due to the short durability of and
19 limited specificity of resistance to a pathogen race. Besides using their resources for
20 pathogenicity, pathogens usually ‘trick’ the host defence system and involve the host
21 genes in favour of their entry and colonisation of the host, so-called susceptibility genes
22 (S genes). In the last two decades, S genes have been used in breeding programs to
23 improve some crop species' resistance against different pathogens. However, the use of
24 mutant S genes for developing resistant crops is often hampered due to the potential

25 pleiotropic effects. To overcome this challenge, New Genomic Techniques (NGTs)
26 provide the tools and platforms to fine-tune the target S gene expression without
27 significant pleiotropic effects. This review summarises the diversity of S gene functions
28 in Arabidopsis and wheat plant species and emphasises the NGTs-based targeted
29 modification of specific S genes for beneficial roles in plants. Furthermore, we
30 implicated the purposeful inclusion of S genes in the resistance breeding programs.

31 Keywords: Plants, pathogens, S genes, Arabidopsis, wheat, New Genomic Techniques,
32 disease resistance, food safety, food security

33 1. Introduction

34 Agriculture has been fundamental to human development in the last 10.000 years [1].
35 However, in the previous decades, challenges for agriculture have increased due to
36 climate change and associated side effects [2]. The reduction of cultivable land [3,4]
37 and stagnation of yields for different crops could severely affect food security [5–7].
38 Pests significantly threaten food security and safety and incur an estimated 4-16% of
39 yield losses globally [8]. However, these estimates are only half of the truth; besides
40 primary losses like yield, quality, cost of control, or loss of income due to less profitable
41 replacement crops, secondary losses by contamination of material or soil-borne
42 diseases must be considered [9]. The study also proposed indirect losses to the farm,
43 rural communities, exporters, or environment. Quite recently, a study overviewed
44 worldwide and regional yield losses in wheat, rice, maize, potato, and soybean [10]. The
45 study describes that the average yield loss ranges between 20-30% worldwide, while in
46 some regions, it can reach up to 40% [10]. This shows that the use of plant protection
47 and more resistant cultivars could increase agricultural yield. According to the crop yield
48 data from France, the increase of crop yield increase is deliberately needed due to the
49 stagnation of yields in the last decade [5–7].

50 Plants are sessile living beings that cannot evade environmental stresses like animals.
51 Therefore, plants have developed a sophisticated immune system to withstand

52 pathogens, as the zig-zag model exemplifies. The model is a multi-layered interaction
53 [11,12] with two interconnected pathways. One basal pathway is activated by
54 extracellular pathogen recognition, and the other intracellular pathway is activated by
55 pathogen-secreted effectors [12,13]. The extracellular pathway can be considered the
56 first line of defence; pattern-recognition receptors (PRRs) in the membrane consist of
57 two parts [14–18]. For example, the intercellular part consists of a receptor domain, a
58 leucine-rich repeat (LRR), or a LysM domain [19]. The intracellular domain usually
59 consists of a kinase domain for signal transduction [19]. These receptors then can
60 recruit receptor kinases in the plasma membrane to increase signal transduction for
61 plant defence [19]. PRRs can detect two distinct groups of molecules: I)
62 Pathogen/microbial-associated molecular patterns (P/MAMPs) and II) host-derived
63 damage-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) [19]. These receptors activate a broad
64 range of plant defence cascades [19]. Pathogens have co-developed mechanisms to
65 suppress plant defence or hijack the cell machinery for their benefit. To do so,
66 pathogens secrete so-called effector proteins (effectors) [11,20–22]. These effectors
67 can interfere with the plant defence response in many ways. One prominent example is
68 the interaction of AvrPto and AvrPtoB from *Pseudomonas syringae* interacting with the
69 FLS2-BAK1 PRR (pattern recognition receptors) complex. AvrPtoBs n-terminal domain
70 can suppress the flg22 response, while the c-terminal domain handles the ubiquitination
71 of the PRR kinase domain [23–25]. Plants have adapted to these effectors and
72 developed intracellular receptors [26]. These receptors are built up by a nucleotide-
73 binding domain (NB) and an LRR domain. They are usually classified into two
74 categories: the Toll/interleukin 1-like receptor (TR) and the coiled-coiled domain (CC)
75 [27–31]. These receptors are often referred to as R genes since their existence is
76 conferring resistance, but not all R genes are receptors [32]. The classical model for
77 these R genes is that they either directly interact with the effector, act as a guard or
78 decoy for the receptor target, or form dimers with other R genes and act as a bait/switch
79 [11,12,28,32,33]. However, this simplified model was recently proposed with some
80 additions to keep it updated. Thordal-Christensen (2020) proposed an iceberg model to
81 understand the complex network of effector and R gene interaction [34]. In this model,

82 Thordal-Christensen proposed that a 2nd ETS effector blocks many R genes. This
83 makes screening for new R genes complicated since 2nd ETS effectors could mask
84 novel R genes or suppress existing R genes [34]. Kourelis and van der Hoorn (2018)
85 and Nguyen, Iswanto et al. (2021) proposed new additions to the existing models. Both
86 reviews expanded the model with new interaction possibilities. One addition to the
87 existing model is executors [32,35]. The TALE binds on its target sequence in a
88 promoter region, but an R gene will be expressed instead of activating a susceptibility
89 gene [32,35]. Another addition is the active loss of susceptibility; here, a gene is actively
90 detoxifying an effector like the HC toxin [32,35]. The opposing idea is the passive loss of
91 susceptibility; here, the R gene is recessive and carries a mutation in the effector target
92 region. This enables its continuous function due to the effector absence [32,35]. These
93 R genes are unmutated and, therefore, are susceptibility genes (S gene). S genes, in
94 general, can be any gene that either eases the infection of a pathogen or is hijacked by
95 pathogens. However, the mutation of an S gene can have severe pleiotropic effects,
96 and therefore, the potential robustness must be determined before [36]. Van Schie and
97 Takken (2014) grouped S genes into three categories.

98 I. Pathogen entry

99 S Genes in this category enable the pathogen to enter the host [36]. This can happen
100 through various mechanisms, by modulating either the function of cuticle/cell wall-
101 associated genes or membrane/cytoskeleton dynamics [37].

102 II. Suppression of defence

103 This S gene category holds genes responsible for suppression of the plant defence
104 responses. The suppression can be either direct involvement in the plant defence
105 pathways or by indirectly regulating other the function of other genes.

106 III. Nutrient acquisition

107 Pathogen uses S genes in this category to acquire nutrients. The channelling of
108 nutrients like sugar into the apoplast/ other cell compartments can be a multi-layer
109 interaction. In addition to sugar transport, the mobilisation of metabolites can also
110 handle pathogen sustenance.

111 In this study, we summarised the functional diversity of S genes identified from the
112 dicotyledon species *Arabidopsis thaliana* and the monocotyledonous species *Triticum*
113 *aestivum* and the relevant pathogens for the specific S gene. Furthermore, we highlight
114 the application of various CRISPR/Cas systems for manipulating the S genes to obtain
115 less/no pleiotropic effects and their inclusion in breeding programs.

116 2. Functions of S genes in response to pathogens

117 S genes are distributed across different gene families with diverse functions in plants.
118 The physiological roles of most S genes in plants have been identified, and their
119 functions across species are well conserved [38–44]. S genes play central roles in
120 primary and secondary cell wall formation, signalling biotic and abiotic stress responses,
121 and nutrient metabolism [45]. Despite their function in plants, they can be hijacked by
122 pathogen effectors for facilitating pathogen entry, suppressing host defence responses,
123 and accelerating nutrient metabolisms for pathogen establishment. Numerous S genes
124 have been reported in *Arabidopsis* and wheat plant species against various plant
125 pathogens (Figure 1, Supplementary Table 1). S genes exhibit contrasting roles in
126 supporting the growth and development of plants and pathogens. To understand the
127 functional category S genes, we collected published studies on S genes for *A. thaliana*
128 and *T. aestivum* as representatives for the dicotyledon and monocotyledon clade,
129 respectively (Table 1). Based on the data, a sunburst diagram was created to
130 understand the relationships between the S gene category, cellular localisation, and
131 host-pathogen interactions (Figure 1). Among all S genes, 49% of the cases were
132 reported from wheat, whereas 51% of the cases were from *Arabidopsis*. (Fig. 1). Out of
133 those cases, most S genes were grouped under the “*Suppression of defence*”. In this S
134 gene category, wheat and *Arabidopsis* were represented by 81% and 66%, respectively

135 (Fig.1). The second largest group represented the “*Pathogen entry and sustenance*”
136 category, with 20% for wheat and 11% for Arabidopsis (Fig. 1). The third category
137 “*Nutrient acquisition*” claimed 15% for wheat and 8% Arabidopsis (Fig. 1).

138 The distribution of the characterised S gene category differed between Arabidopsis and
139 wheat. In wheat, the research is focused mainly on S genes against fungal pathogens
140 (a total of 90 %, 82% of these were biotrophic and 18% necrotrophic) and few on
141 bacteria (5%), insects (3%) and nematodes (2%). In Arabidopsis, the research is more
142 evenly distributed; this could be due to the use of Arabidopsis as a model plant for most
143 studies. In this regard, the S gene distribution revealed 29% against bacterial
144 pathogens, 19% against fungi, 30% against nematodes, 19% against insects and 3%
145 against oomycetes (Fig. 1). Interestingly, in wheat, most targets against biotrophic fungi
146 were either “*Suppression of defence*” or “*Nutrient acquisition*.” In contrast, targets
147 against necrotrophic fungi with one exception were exclusively found under the category
148 “*Pathogen entry and sustenance*” (Fig. 1). Alike in wheat, most of the Arabidopsis S
149 genes under the “*Suppression of defence*” category were against necrotrophic fungi.
150 We could only find one candidate belonging to the “*Pathogen entry and sustenance*”
151 group (Fig. 1). To further understand the S genes described in the literature and their
152 role, we focused on each of the four pathogen groups bacteria, fungi, nematodes, and
153 insects.

154 2.1. Bacteria

155 Many of the plant-associated bacteria are pathogens that impair the growth and
156 development of plants [46]. Pathogenic bacteria manipulate the host S genes to
157 promote disease development like other pathogens. For this purpose, bacterial
158 pathogens deploy several effectors to manipulate host S genes and effectively suppress
159 various layers of host defence responses [47–50]. Targeting S genes by bacterial
160 effectors creates a compatible bacteria-plant interaction at every stage of disease
161 progression. Various S genes and their interacting bacterial effectors have been

162 reported from multiple plant species and associated bacterial pathogens, as reviewed in
163 [51].

164 *Pathogen entry and sustenance*

165 Like other diseases, the development of bacterial diseases is the collective effects of
166 pathogen entry and establishment, host defence suppression, nutrient acquisition, and
167 transport of effectors into the host cells [52–54]. However, in contrast to other
168 pathogens, bacteria lack structures like the appressoria of fungi and oomycetes to
169 penetrate the cell wall structure of plants. Therefore, before the translocation of effectors
170 and disease induction, bacteria require openings such as stomata, hydathodes, or
171 wounds as entry channels into the host. Plants activate the stomatal closure upon
172 pathogen attack to restrict the entry of pathogens [55], and bacteria pathogens enable
173 the opening of the stomata by interacting genes participating in stomata dynamics.

174 Receptor-like kinases (RLKs) mediate plant immunity signalling and are targets of
175 bacterial effectors. BIK1 (Botrytis Induced Kinase 1) is one of the RLKs that mediate PTI
176 stomata closure and is targeted by the bacterial pathogen *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv.
177 *Oryzae* (Xoo) effector (XopR) [49]. The XopR-BIK1 interacting module initiates the
178 suppression of stomata closure for easy pathogen entry. Another RK, LecRK, negatively
179 regulates stomatal immunity upstream of the reactive oxygen species (ROS)
180 biosynthesis, and the loss of function mutants increased resistance to *P. syringae* pv.
181 tomato [56]. In Arabidopsis, an adverse immune regulator, RIN4 protein, interacts with
182 the plasma membrane H⁺-ATPase, AHA1 and AHA2. The activation of H⁺-ATPase by
183 RIN4 induces stomata opening, enabling bacterial entry into the host cells [57].

184 *Suppression of defence*

185 To survive and replicate, most bacterial pathogens secrete effectors directly inside the
186 cells and modulate the function of the target S genes in the host [58]. So far, most of the
187 target S genes during bacterial infection are categorised under the suppression of host
188 defence responses (Figure 1, Supplementary Table). The AtWRKY38 and AtWRKY62

189 transcription factors (TFs) are induced in an NPR1-dependent manner by salicylic acid
190 (SA) or by virulent *P. syringae* and act as negative regulators of plant basal defence
191 [59]. Single and double mutants of these TFs enhanced resistance to *P. syringae* by
192 increasing the expression of the SA-regulated Pathogenesis-Related1 (PR1) gene in
193 *Arabidopsis*.

194 Other *Arabidopsis* TFs such as ANAC019, ANAC055, and ANAC072, activated by *P.*
195 *syringae* toxin Coronatine, induce stomatal reopening and bacterial spread in both local
196 and systemic tissues [60] (Fig. 2). The activation of these NAC TFs suppresses SA
197 biosynthesis and metabolism by repressing the expression of the biosynthetic gene
198 ICS1 and activating the metabolism gene BSMT1. The upregulation of BSMT1
199 suppresses the accumulation of SA via the conversion of SA into inactive volatile methyl
200 SA and compromises resistance to *P. syringae*. Likewise, the wheat NAC TF gene
201 TaNAC1 overexpression induced enhanced susceptibility to *P. syringae* DC3000 in
202 *Arabidopsis* [61]. TaNAC1 negatively regulates plant disease resistance by suppressing
203 PR1 and PR2, thereby modulating the plant JA- and SA-signalling defence cascades.

204 *Arabidopsis* *cir1* and *cir2-2* genes are defined as negative regulators of disease
205 resistance. The mutants of *cir1* and *cir2-2* increased the constitutive expression of
206 defence genes and enhanced resistance against *P. syringae* pv. *tomato* [62,63]. The
207 *cir1* mutation-mediated resistance operates upstream of SA, JA, and ET accumulation,
208 and both JA and ET sensitivity are required for *cir1*-mediated resistance against *P.*
209 *syringae* pv. *tomato*. Cellulose synthases (CESAs) are localised in the plasma
210 membrane and essential for cellulose synthesis. Pathogenic bacteria target CESAs to
211 modulate the integrity of the host cell wall for ease of entry and propagation. The
212 *Arabidopsis* CESAs, CESA4 (IRX5), CESA7 (IRX3), and CESA8 (IRX1) are involved in
213 the synthesis of the secondary cell wall, and mutation in these proteins conferred
214 enhanced resistance to the soil-borne bacterium *Ralstonia solanacearum* [64]. Likewise,
215 the gene product of WAT1 (Walls Are Thin1) is required for secondary cell-wall
216 deposition, and its WAT1 mutant conferred broad-spectrum resistance to vascular
217 bacterial pathogens like *R. solanacearum* and *X. campestris* pv. *campestris* [65].

218 The mechanism of WAT1 mutation involves increasing the SA levels and repression of
219 indole metabolism. Like CESAs, lipid transport proteins (LTPs) are known as positive
220 regulators of plant resistance. However, pathogen- and ABA-inducible LTP3 negatively
221 regulate plant immunity by enhancing the ABA biosynthesis and suppressing the SA
222 level in an ABA-independent manner [66]. In addition, LTP4, the closest homolog of
223 LTP3, functions in a redundant manner with LTP3 by modulating the ABA pathway. Like
224 LTP3 and LTP4, the TAL effector (Tal8) of the wheat pathogen *X. translucens* pv.
225 *undulosa* activate the rate-limiting enzymes, TaNCED_5BS and TaNCED_5DS, in the
226 ABA biosynthesis [47]. Upon their activation, the higher ABA level causes a drop in
227 transpiration and water loss that supports the spread of bacteria in the infected leaves
228 (Fig. 2). Moreover, the activation of TaNCED_5BS and TaNCED_5DS represses the
229 expression of the central defence gene TaNPR1 [67–69].

230 Plants generate ROS to defend against pathogens. Pathogenic bacteria suppress or
231 increase the production of ROS to induce host susceptibility [45]. To successfully infect
232 plants, hemi(bio)trophs suppress ROS production, whereas necrotrophs stimulate ROS
233 production [70]. Bacterial infection and MAMP stimulation upregulate the expression of
234 SAM-MT1 and SAM-MT2 methyltransferases [48]. *X. campestris* pv. *campestris* (*Xcc*)
235 effector AvrXccB interacts with the SAM-MT1/SAM-MT2 complex to suppress innate
236 immunity (Fig. 2). The AvrXccB-SAM-MT1/SAM-MT2 interaction module suppresses
237 ROS production and callose deposition to induce susceptibility.

238 *Nutrient acquisition*

239 Once they enter the host and suppress host immune responses, pathogens, including
240 bacteria, require nutrients to sustain, proliferate, and cause diseases. Bacteria bind their
241 effectors to the promoters of S genes to obtain nutrients from the host or direct the
242 physical interaction of effectors and the target S gene product. Though not described
243 yet for Arabidopsis and wheat, the binding of TAL effectors upregulates the expression
244 of the SWEET family of sugar transporters, increasing the channelling of sugars to the
245 apoplast [71–73]. In contrast, the Ripl effector of *R. solanacearum* physically interacts

246 with calmodulin and glutamate decarboxylases (GADs) and promotes calmodulin
247 binding to GADs for activation [50]. Consequently, GADs catalyse the biosynthesis of
248 gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA), and the bacteria use GABA as a nitrogen source to
249 replicate and cause symptoms (Fig. 2). In Arabidopsis, the mutation of AtGAD1,
250 AtGAD2, and AtGAD4 genes reduces GABA levels and inhibits pathogen GABA uptake
251 leading to compromised bacterial growth and delayed symptom development.

252 2.2. Fungi

253 Fungi are agronomically important plant pests that negatively impact food safety and
254 security [9,10]. Fungal pathogens can be distinguished from other pathogens based on
255 their lifestyle and interaction with the host for nutrients. Biotrophic fungi feed on living
256 plant cells, whereas necrotrophic fungi access nutrients from dead plant cells [74].

257 2.2.1. Biotrophic

258 *Pathogen entry and sustenance*

259 TaS3 is the homolog of ULP1, a small ubiquitin-related modifier (SUMO) specific
260 protease involved in cell-cycle progression. It represents the only S gene involved in
261 pathogen entry and sustenance. The overexpression of TaS3 has increased plant
262 susceptibility to powdery mildew, whereas its suppression has diminished the pathogen
263 penetration by 19 % [75].

264 *Suppression of defence*

265 In Arabidopsis, the characterised S genes are exclusively grouped under the
266 “Suppression of Defence” category. Here, we find CESA4, CESA7, and CESA8 from the
267 cellulose synthase family, whose loss of function mutation conferred increased
268 resistance to *Hyaloperonospora parasitica* [76]. The mutation in these genes severely
269 affects the hormone interplay in plant defence responses and confer resistance [76].
270 However, mutations in cell wall-associated genes usually have severe side effects on
271 plant development and morphology, making them undesirable targets for plant breeding

272 [77]. In contrast to Arabidopsis, S genes against biotrophic fungi in wheat lie in all
273 categories, though most S genes are involved in suppressing host defence. Most wheat
274 S genes against biotrophic fungi were from the WRKY and NAC transcription factors
275 (Fig. 1). In this regard, various TaNAC with different modes of action were identified and
276 characterised against the biotrophic fungi, *Puccinia striiformis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pst*) [78,79].
277 TaNAC1 suppresses the expression of resistance-related genes involved in the SA
278 signalling pathway [78]. In this regard, the role of TaNAC2 is different. Virus-induced
279 gene silencing (VIGS) of TaNAC2 in wheat showed that TaNAC2 is involved in
280 regulating H₂O₂ levels in response to *Pst* [79]. The silencing of TaNAC2 leads to a
281 significant increase in H₂O₂ at the early infection state and could reduce hyphae growth
282 but not the disease symptoms in general [79]. Like TaNAC2, TaNAC30 is also involved
283 in the H₂O₂ response, and the silencing of TaNAC30 by VIGS enhanced resistance to
284 *Pst* through accumulated H₂O₂ response [80]. In response to *Pst*, TaNAC21 and
285 TaNAC22 are targeted by the microRNA miR164 [81]. The necrotic area to *Pst* infection
286 was increased in the knocked-down wheat plants, while hyphal growth was restricted
287 [81]. Hence, TaNAC21/22-mediated resistance involves programmed cell death as a
288 defence response to *Pst* infection. So far, no effector has been reported from *Pst*,
289 though PgtSR1 has been identified from the pathogen *P. graminis* f. sp. *tritici* (*Pgt*) [82].
290 PgtSR1 suppresses the RNA silencing mechanism after infection, reducing the
291 abundance of defence-regulating miRNAs [82]. *Pst* could secrete a similar effector to
292 suppress the plant defence involving the TaNAC21/22. Besides the NAC, WRKY TFs
293 are also involved in plant defence against biotrophic fungi. TaWRKY49 and TaWRKY62
294 regulate SA- and jasmonic acid (JA)-responsive genes [83]. In contrast to TaWRKY49
295 and TaWRKY62, TaEIL1 is an ethylene-responsive TF and highly upregulated at 18-
296 and 24-hrs post-inoculation (hpi) with *Pst* [84]. After wounding and hormone elicitors
297 treatments, TaEIL1 was upregulated in plants, mainly after methyl jasmonate and
298 abscisic acid (ABA) [84]. The VIGS of TaEIL1 resulted in reduced susceptibility to *Pst*
299 infection and the upregulation of several defence-related genes like TaPR1, TaPR2,
300 TaPR5, and TaPAL [84]. Most TFs involved in suppressing the defence are somehow

301 linked to the hormonal defence pathway, making the axis of attack for biotrophic wheat
302 pathogens.

303 Besides TFs, other S genes against biotrophic fungi that suppress host defence
304 responses have been reported. One of the groups is the TaMLOs, where a mutation in
305 the gene confers resistance to powdery mildew [85–87]. MLOs have been extensively
306 studied [87] and are known to be involved in several biotic and abiotic stress responses,
307 growth and development, such as reproduction and thigmotropism [87]. However, MLO-
308 mediated resistance to powdery mildew usually comes with a cost, as it is accompanied
309 by pleiotropy and yield penalty [88]. In recent advances, thanks to New Genomic
310 Techniques (NGTs), novel mutant lines were generated without penalties of agronomic
311 traits [87]. However, transferring MLOs-mediated resistance results from one plant
312 species to another has not been easy. In *Arabidopsis*, only a triple knock-out of
313 *AtMLO2/6/12* leads to complete resistance to downy mildew. The resistance mechanism
314 is like the *pmr4* mutation, which relies on SA-induced hypersensitive response [89].
315 Meanwhile, in tomatoes, peas, rice, or pepper, only a single MLO is responsible for
316 powdery mildew resistance [90–93]. Histone deacetylation forms another group of S
317 genes involving suppression of host defence in response to biotrophic fungi infection
318 (Fig. 1). *TaHDT701*, *TaHDA6* and *TaHOS15* are involved in the histone deacetylase
319 complex [94,95]. This complex governs the fine-tuning of defence responses to
320 *Blumeria graminis* f.sp. *tritici* (*Bgt*), mainly suppressing the defence response after
321 infection [94,95]. However, the broad spectrum of studies on S genes shows that more
322 than one group of genes are responsible for susceptibility to pathogens (Fig. 1). They
323 can be in many distinct groups, ranging from the in-detail explained TFs over to genes
324 involved in signalling pathways like the G-protein *TaROP10*, the invertase *Ta-A/N-Inv1*
325 involved in sucrose metabolism, or the aminotransferase *TaBCAT1* [96–98]. Some S
326 genes' have been found to partner with effectors. The model pathogen *Pst* is one well-
327 understood pathogen, and some effectors and their S gene targets are already defined
328 in the literature. *Pst_12806* targets *TaISP*, a subunit of the Cyt b6/f complex [99] (Fig. 2).
329 ISPs play a crucial role in photosynthesis but also in the production of ROS and

330 indirectly affect the expression of defence-related genes [100]. Though the role of
331 *Pst*_12806 is not yet fully understood, it could still be possible that *Pst* is manipulating
332 the host photosynthesis. More importantly, *Pst* suppresses programmed cell death by
333 modifying chloroplast-derived ROS production [99]. A similar effect has been observed
334 in the interplay between the effector, *Pst*18363 and a nucleotide diphosphate hydrolase,
335 *TaNUDX23* [101]. *TaNUDX23* is targeted and stabilised by the effector *Pst*18363 (Fig. 2)
336 [101]. This stabilisation in the early infection stage reduces ROS accumulation after
337 infection. However, silencing of *TaNUDX23* would increase ROS accumulation and
338 reduce susceptibility (Fig. 2) [101]. Even though the mechanisms in which *Pst* interferes
339 with the plant defence response differ, the outcomes are similar: a reduced ROS
340 accumulation, thus inhibiting cell death [99,101]. *TaCSN5* is the COP 9 SIGNALOSOME
341 (CSN), a protein complex responsible for the ubiquitin-proteasome system [102]. In the
342 regular interaction between *Pst* and wheat, *TaCSN5* is upregulated at five dpi; however,
343 silencing studies showed that silenced *TaCSN5* would lead to an upregulation of *PR1*
344 and *PDF1.2* at one dpi [102]. In the two mutants, *PR1* was upregulated at two dpi.
345 Further infection studies revealed that the amount of haustoria was significantly higher
346 at five dpi compared to early infection stages. The early *PR1* induction would hinder the
347 successful host colonisation of *Pst* [102]. However, so far, no effector targeting *TaCSN5*
348 has been found, and the current data highly suggests that a haustoria-secreted effector
349 might manipulate *TaCSN5* and reduce the host's defence.

350 Calcineurin B-like protein (CBL)-interacting protein kinases (CIPKs) participate in
351 defence responses. The knockdown of the wheat CIPKs (*TaCIPK14*) significantly
352 improved the resistance of wheat plants to *Pst*, whereas *TaCIPK14* overexpression
353 enhanced susceptibility to *Pst* by suppressing ROS accumulation and expression of
354 pathogenesis-related genes [103]. Triple knockout of the three *Tacipk14* homoeoalleles
355 via CRISPR/Cas9 provides broad-spectrum resistance to *Pst* without any pleiotropic
356 effects.

357 *Pathogen entry and sustenance*

358 Though most S genes manipulated by biotrophic fungi are involved in the suppression
359 of host defence, few S genes have also been identified to play roles in pathogen entry
360 and sustenance or nutrient acquisition (Fig. 1). For entry and sustenance, *Bgt* targets
361 two cuticular wax biosynthesis genes, TaKCS6 and TaECR [104,105]. Silencing of
362 TaECR resulted in a significant increase in non-germinated conidia [104]. *Bgt* needs to
363 sense the waxy cuticle to initiate conidiation. Likewise, this scenario of *Bgt* conidiation
364 because of wax cuticular accumulation was also confirmed in the TaKCS6-knockdown
365 study [105]. The cuticular wax synthesis was altered in both cases, and a reduced or
366 incomplete wax layer impaired *Bgt* germination (Fig. 2) [104,105]. So far, no effector has
367 been reported from *Bgt* that interferes with this mechanism. Since the cuticle is a basal
368 layer on the epidermal cells, it is unlikely that there will be an effector stabilising this
369 process. The TaWIN1 TF and its partner, the kinase TaCDK8, are also involved in the
370 biosynthesis of the cuticle and very long-chain aldehydes [106]. It has been shown that
371 silencing one of the partners could hinder *Bgt* germination on the wheat leaves [106].

372 *Nutrient acquisition*

373 Upon infection, biotrophic fungi have been shown to upregulate the expression of TFs
374 and transporters, specifically sugar and ammonium transporters. These include the
375 sugar transporter (TaSTP3/6/13) and TFs (TaWRKY19/61/82) (Fig. 1). However, it is
376 essential to note that all the three TFs are involved in the regulation of the sugar
377 transporter TaSTP3 [107]. TaSTP3 is localised in the plasma membrane and transports
378 hexoses and sucrose, making it an essential target for *Pst*. Though a knock-out or
379 silencing of TaSTP3 was not generated, single knockouts of the three WRKY TFs and
380 overexpression of TaSTP3 showed that TaSTP3 is vital for the effective infection and
381 colonisation of *Pst* (Fig. 2) [107]. Likewise, another sugar transporter, TaSTP6,
382 facilitates the supply of sugar to *Pst* throughout infection and colonisation [108]. TaSTP6
383 expression is upregulated after ABA treatment or inoculation with *Pst*, whereas
384 TaSTP13 is upregulated after *Pst* infection and different abiotic/biotic stresses or
385 hormones [108,109]. So far, no effector interacting with the TaSTPs or the WRKY

386 transcription factors has been reported. However, *Pst* or other biotrophic fungi likely
387 manipulate the expression of sugar transporters [107–109].

388 2.2.2. Necrotrophic

389 S genes identified so far against necrotrophic fungi in Arabidopsis and wheat are
390 exclusively either in the suppression of defence or pathogen entry and sustenance
391 group (Fig. 1). However, suppression of defence might be misleading since the general
392 assumption for necrotrophic pathogens is to facilitate cell death to feed on dead tissues.

393 *Suppression of defence*

394 As described for biotrophic fungi, necrotrophic fungi also involve CESA4/7/8 during
395 infection. This is due to the involvement of these genes in the basal hormone regulation.
396 Therefore, we focus more on two other S genes found in Arabidopsis. LOV1, a coiled-
397 coil-nucleotide-binding-leucine-rich repeat (CC-NB-LRR) protein, is targeted by the
398 compound victorin from *Cochliobolus victoriae* [110]. It confers victorin sensitivity and
399 disease susceptibility against *C. victoriae* infection [110] (Fig. 2). LOV1 is a member of
400 the RPP8 family and is the only gene conferring resistance to *C. victoriae* [111]. LOV1
401 and other genes identified by Gilbert and Wolpert (2013) appear to function in the
402 RPP8-mediated plant defence and cell death pathway [111]. The authors speculated
403 that LOV1 could be a guard R gene exploited by *C. victoriae* via victorin [111].
404 Cir mutations induce the constitutive expression of defence-associated genes and
405 confer resistance against biotrophic and necrotrophic pathogens [112]. In Arabidopsis,
406 Cir3 is involved in the JA/ET-regulated plant defence pathway, and functional Cir3
407 suppresses several genes in the JA/ET pathway. Hence, the Cir3 mutated plants
408 showed resistance against *Botrytis cinerea* [112]. Though not yet explicitly identified, a
409 wheat candidate S gene has been mapped on the QTL Sf-Fhb-7AS, suppressing host
410 defence responses during FHB infection (Supplementary Table).

411 *Pathogen entry and sustenance*

412 For necrotrophic fungi, most S genes identified so far participate in pathogen entry and
413 sustenance (Supplementary Table). In Arabidopsis, the MYB46 TF orchestrates the cell

414 wall-associated protein expression of different plant defence genes, like extracellular
415 peroxidases [113]. MYB46 regulates expressions by binding to cis-regulatory elements
416 in the 5' promoter region of the target genes [113]. Ep5C, a type III peroxidase, is
417 upregulated in the *myb46* mutant [113]. Though *myb46* knockdown mutant plants resist
418 *B. cinerea*, they were susceptible to *P. syringae*. ANGUSTIFOLIA, a plant homolog of a
419 mammalian C-terminal binding protein (CtBP), antagonistically regulates plant
420 resistance to necrotrophic pathogens [114]. ANGUSTIFOLIA binds to MYB46 and
421 represses the transcription. The ANGUSTIFOLIA overexpressing plants were more
422 susceptible to *P. syringae* [114]. ANGUSTIFOLIA mediates transcriptional co-regulation
423 of MYB46 and WRKY33 for optimised defence against biotrophic and necrotrophic
424 pathogens via regulated SA and JA/ET pathways [114].

425 The *Parastagonospora nodorum* (*Psn*)-wheat pathosystems identified S genes against
426 necrotrophic fungi in wheat. In addition to the five well-characterized effectors [115,116],
427 additional putative effectors have been found in the pan-genome studies of different *Psn*
428 strains [117]. The ToxA effector is secreted by *Psn*, *Pyrenophora tritici-repentis* and
429 *Bipolaris sorokiniana* and targets Tsn1 and TaNHL10 in wheat (Fig. 2) [118]. The ToxA–
430 Tsn1 interaction is light-dependent, indicating Tsn1's role in the chloroplast. However,
431 Tsn1-mediated susceptibility lies in the downregulation of genes involved in ROS
432 detoxification (Fig. 2) [115,116]. Tsn1 appears to be an NBS-LRR resistance gene;
433 however, pathogens manipulate it via ToxA to facilitate PCD [115,116]. The other target,
434 TaNHL10, is also targeted by ToxA but via a different interaction module [119].
435 Interestingly, the TaNHL10–ToxA interaction functions in the same pathway as the Tsn1–
436 ToxA [115,116,119]. However, it seems that when ToxA cannot bind to TaNHL10,
437 necrosis in Tsn1 dominant wheat lines was prevented [119]. Though the entire
438 mechanism is not yet understood, TaNHL10 is responsible for the endocytosis of ToxA.
439 This brings the antagonist into the host cells, where it binds to Tsn1, hijacking it and
440 manipulating the host to execute PCD [116,119].

441 *Psn* not only induces PCD via the ToxA effector; its SnTox1, using a similar mechanism
442 as ToxA, targets TaSnn1, a cell wall-associated PRR-Kinase, during infection [115,116].

443 TaSnn1 initiates the typical plant defence cascade, resulting in different layers of
444 responses and eventually resulting in PCD (Fig. 2). According to Friesen and Faris
445 (2021), SnTox1 is the first effector reported so far for targeting a PRR [115]. SnTox1
446 binds to chitin and prevents the degradation of the *Psn* cell wall by the plant chitinases
447 [115,116]. In addition to the ToxA and SnTox1, *Psn* activates the SnTox3–TaSnn3,
448 SnTox5–TaSnn5 and the SnTox267-TaSnn2/TaSnn6/TaSnn7 interacting modules to
449 enable effective entry and sustenance (Fig. 2) [115,116]. Based on *Psn* effectors, an
450 effector can target multiple proteins to manipulate host defence for entry into the host
451 cell, guard the pathogen against plant chitinases, or enable colonisation of the
452 mesophyll layer [116]. In general, necrotrophic fungi manipulate the host plant defence
453 to induce PCD. Except for QTL Sf-Fhb-7AS, which is involved in the suppression of host
454 defence responses, all the discovered S genes from wheat exclusively participate in
455 pathogen entry and sustenance (Fig. 1). Deleting QTL Sf-Fhb-7AS contributes to 50–
456 60% of type 2 FHB resistance in wheat and reduced DON content in infected plants
457 [120]. The DON mycotoxin is produced by *Fusarium graminearum* and is considered as
458 one virulence factor to overcome plant defence [121,122].

459 2.3. Herbivores

460 2.3.1. Nematodes

461 Plant-parasitic nematodes (PPNs) are obligate biotrophs dependent only on living cells.
462 For parasitism, PPNs create feeding sites from the redifferentiation of host root cells that
463 are believed to be regulated by pathogenicity factors secreted by PPNs [123,124]. Like
464 other pathogens, PPNs regulate the S genes in their favour to colonise the host. GWAS
465 and transcriptome studies have identified the S genes, HIPP27 and BZR1, against
466 PPNs in Arabidopsis. HIPP27 facilitates cyst nematode infection and the efficient
467 development of nematode-feeding sites in roots [125]. In a separate study,
468 CRISPR/Cas9-mediated KO of HIPP27 reduced nematode infection without any growth
469 defects [126]. BZR1 is a TF that regulates the susceptibility of Arabidopsis plants to *M.*
470 *incognita* [127]. In the *bzr1-1D* mutants, the BZR1 knockout has reduced the number of

471 PPN eggs, total root length and constitutive upregulation of PR1. Thus, the loss of
472 susceptibility in the *bzr1-1D* mutant improved host basal immunity and limited the
473 expansion of nematode-induced giant root cells and the reproductive success of PPNs.
474 Another S gene to PPNs is ERF6, a central regulator of abiotic stress tolerance in plants
475 independent of ethylene signalling [128]. The Arabidopsis line harbouring a T-DNA insert
476 encoding ERF6 was infested with an average of 28% more egg masses per plant than
477 the corresponding wild-type plants. ERF6 regulates the ACO2 and ACO3 expression
478 and affects the conversion of ACC into ethylene in the nematode-infected roots.

479 The amino acid permease 6 of Arabidopsis (*AtAAP6*) and wheat (*TaAAP6*) are linked to
480 susceptibility to cyst nematode *Heterodera filipjevi* [129]. They are considered
481 susceptibility factor genes due to their upregulation in the nematode-infected roots of
482 susceptible wheat genotype and the nematode-induced syncytia of infected Arabidopsis
483 roots. The *AtAAP6* knockout mutants reduced the number and size of developing
484 females and the size of female-associated syncytia, suggesting the importance of AAP6
485 in cyst nematode parasitism. *MIOX4*, a cell wall polysaccharides biosynthesis gene, is
486 also highly upregulated in syncytia during infection by the plant parasitic nematode *H.*
487 *schachtii*. The simultaneous knockout of *miox1/2/4/5* improved the resistance of
488 Arabidopsis plants to nematodes without affecting the cell wall composition.

489 The involvement of distinct phytohormonal pathways is extensively studied against
490 groups of pathogens. In contrast to SA or JA, which are involved in activating defence
491 response against biotrophic and necrotrophic pathogens, ABA may regulate resistance
492 or susceptibility depending on the pathogens' lifestyle. In this regard, the effect of ABA
493 on nematode resistance /susceptibility was examined by targeting various ABA pathway
494 genes [130]. Genes involved in ABA-turnover (*ABI1*, *ABI2*, *ABI5*, *PYL5*, *PYL6*,
495 *CYP707A1* and *CYP707A4*) showed different expression patterns in the nematode-
496 infected roots of Arabidopsis [130]. And genes that participate in ABA signalling (*ABI2*,
497 *ABI5*) and ABA metabolism (*CYP707A4*) were upregulated, whereas genes of ABA
498 receptors (*PYL5* and *PYL6*) showed no change of expression. Arabidopsis mutants for
499 *ABI1*, *ABI2*, *ABI5*, *CYP707A1* or *CYP707A4* genes improved resistance to *H. schachtii*,

500 owing to diminished numbers of fully developed females. On the contrary, mutations in
501 *PYL5* or *PYL6* genes did not influence the number of female nematodes.

502 The basic helix–loop–helix transcription factors (bHLH) govern the transcription of target
503 genes by binding to the promoters and regulating developmental processes and stress
504 responses. The Arabidopsis bHLH *bHLH25* and *bHLH27* support cyst nematode
505 parasitism [131]. The overexpression of either or both bHLH genes exhibited altered
506 morphology of roots and shoots, as well as an increased susceptibility to *H. schachtii*.
507 Due to the functional redundancies in the bHLH gene families, single mutants of *bhlh25*
508 or *bhlh27* showed no phenotype change. However, double mutants exhibited reduced
509 susceptibility to *H. schachtii*. Thus, the co-expression of both transcription factor genes
510 is indispensable for cyst nematode parasitism.

511 In addition to the GWAS and transcriptome analysis, small RNA-sequencing and
512 subsequent functional validation have aided the identification of more S genes against
513 PPNs. MicroRNAs (miRNAs) are 20–24 nucleotides long non-coding RNAs that act as
514 crucial transcriptional and post-transcriptional regulators of gene expression in diverse
515 biological processes. The overexpression of miR396a/b resulted in post-transcriptional
516 repression of GRF1/GRF3 expression, thereby reducing syncytium size and arresting
517 nematode development [132]. Another miR858-MYB83 regulatory module is also
518 involved in PPN parasitism. The overexpression of miR858 significantly decreased the
519 transcript levels of MYB83, resulting in a considerable reduction of susceptibility in the
520 Arabidopsis plants [133]. The overexpression of miR827 post-transcriptionally silenced
521 its NLA target gene in the syncytium [134]. The miR827 is a nematode-activated miRNA
522 in the syncytium that suppresses immune responses to establish infection and cause
523 disease. Inactivation of miR827 activity through target mimicry or overexpression of a
524 miR827-resistant cDNA of NLA produced the opposite phenotype of reduced plant
525 susceptibility to *H. schachtii*. The overexpression of miR159 in galls repressed the
526 expression of the miR159 target MYB33 and restricted its expression to the initial
527 stages of infection [135]. The miR159abc Arabidopsis mutant was less susceptible to
528 the root-knot nematode (RKN) *Meloidogyne incognita* in a similar study.

529 2.3.2. Insects

530 Like other pathogens, insects cause significant yield loss in the field and storage. The
531 primary source of genetic resistance for insect control relies on R genes. The progress
532 in S gene discovery against insects is lagging despite the increasing interest in using S
533 genes to control other pathogens. One agronomically important insect pathogen is the
534 Hessian fly gall midge (*Mayetiola destructor*), a gall-inducing and destructive insect pest
535 of wheat [136]. Even though several effective R genes against *M. destructor* have been
536 identified in wheat [137], all known R genes are sensitive to higher temperatures and
537 are ineffective in controlling *M. destructor* above 28 °C [138]. The wheat S gene against
538 *M. destructor*, *M. destructor* susceptibility gene-1 (Mds-1), is a heat-shock protein highly
539 induced in wheat seedlings during compatible interactions with *M. destructor* infestation
540 [139]. Silencing of Mds-1 by RNA interference confers immunity to all *M. destructor*
541 biotypes in the known susceptible wheat genotypes (Fig. 2). Mds-1-silenced plants also
542 showed reduced lesion formation after *Bgt* infection. The Russian wheat aphid
543 (*Diuraphis noxia*) is one of the major economically important insect pests of wheat
544 worldwide, more specifically on winter wheat populations in the western United States
545 [140]. Controlling the pest has been the major hurdle due to the emergence of new *D.*
546 *noxia* biotypes virulent to existing R genes, where the *D. noxia* –host interaction relies
547 on R gene-mediated resistance, conferring race- or biotype-specific resistance
548 [141,142]. On the contrary, an upregulated S gene in the susceptible wheat cultivar in
549 response to the *D. noxia* infestation has been targeted for knockout to obtain more
550 durable pest resistance. Silencing of the (1,3;1,4)- β -glucanase gene was achieved
551 using the Barley stripe mosaic virus-mediated VIGS approach [143]. In the silenced
552 wheat plant, aphids had a lower daily reproduction rate and more extended
553 prenymphopositional periods than the control plants (Fig. 2). The reproduction rate of
554 Aphids and symptom development in the host plant showed linear relationships with
555 (1,3;1,4)- β -glucanase transcript levels.

556 Aphids are harmful insects that consume phloem sap, damaging plants directly and
557 serving as vectors for transmitting plant viruses. It's worth noting that the effectiveness

558 of R genes in combating aphids varies greatly depending on the species. Meanwhile,
559 incorporating S genes into a plant's defence mechanism provides broader protection
560 against diverse aphid genotypes. Endoplasmic reticulum-localized transporter PIN5
561 favoured aphid virulence via tight regulation of auxin [144]. The study also examined the
562 performance of knock-out mutant lines of S genes against two aphid species, *Myzus*
563 *persicae*, *Myzus cerasi* and *Rhopalosiphum pisum*. The knock-out mutants of the
564 selected S genes showed altered resistance to *Myzus persicae* and *Myzus cerasi*.
565 Among them, the knock-out of *gat1_2.1*, *pin5*, and *miox4* slightly affected the
566 performance of *M. cerasi*. However, the mutant lines of *pin5*, *miox4*, *sqp2*, *dmp2*, *tat3*
567 and *gat1_2.1* significantly reduce the reproduction of *M. persicae*. In contrast to both
568 aphid species, none of the mutant lines affected the performance of *R. padi*, indicating
569 the tight regulation of S genes depending on a specific aphid species.

570 3. NGTs could revolutionise plant breeding for resistance

571 NGTs are molecular techniques for creating targeted modifications in the genomes of
572 living organisms. They appeared in the 90s of the last century, and zinc-finger
573 nucleases (ZFNs) were the first to be reported. These classes of nucleases use DNA-
574 binding zinc finger protein domains fused with endonucleases like FokI for subsequent
575 targeting, binding and cleavage of the target DNA [145–148]. ZFNs have been exploited
576 to develop important plant traits [149–151]. Following ZFNs, transcription activator-like
577 endonucleases (TALENs) were developed based on a FokI nuclease domain and DNA
578 binding TALE repeats fusion [152–154]. In the last decade, TALENs had a much higher
579 adoption and extensive use in plants than ZFNs. [151,155–157]. A few years after the
580 development of TALENs, Charpentier and Doudna proposed the CRISPR/Cas system
581 that uses the Cas9 endonuclease for precise genome editing (GE) [158], leading to the
582 Nobel Prize in Chemistry 2020 [159]. In contrast to ZFNs and TALENs that rely on large
583 Zinc-Finger or TALEN proteins, CRISPR/Cas9-mediated GE depends on guide RNA
584 (gRNA) containing a target-specific sequence (protospacer) and Cas endonuclease to
585 navigate the Cas and modify the target DNA [160–162].

586 3.1. Genome Editing: What is in our toolbox?

587 The CRISPR/Cas9 system has undergone several modifications to increase its activity
588 and specificity. Some of these modifications include deleting the RuvC domain for
589 developing a nickase [158,163], the fusion of a VirD2 relaxase to the Cas9 to facilitate
590 homology-directed repair [164], CRISPR/Cas with relaxed PAM preferences [165–168],
591 and more recently a new variant of near-PAM-less Cas9 variant, SpRY. SpRY could
592 enable a broad spectrum of new targets in plant genomes [169]. The SpRY has enabled
593 the targeting of broader genomic regions in plants [169,170]. Besides the SpRY,
594 PhieABE is a PAM-less base editing system that aids the change of single nucleotide
595 bases in the DNA [170]. Base editors are another CRISPR/Cas system addition that
596 enables single-base conversions. Initially, it aided the conversion of G>C and A>T, but
597 now all combinations are available [171–173] This low-invasive CRISPR/Cas variant
598 could be used to re-design proteins and modify Cis-regulatory sites (CREs) and miRNA
599 binding sites. The system allows minimal protein structure and function changes but
600 abolishes the regulatory binding, as shown for the rice flagellin receptor OsFLK2 [174].

601 The prime editing system comprises of a pegRNA (prime editing guide RNA) and a
602 reverse transcriptase fused to the catalytically impaired Cas9 [175,176]. The pegRNA
603 contains sequences for the sgRNA and the desired edit [175]. Prime editing has
604 enabled point mutations, insertions, and deletions in various plant genes, including rice
605 and wheat [177]. In addition to new enzyme combinations for prime editing, new tools
606 for pegRNA design have also been explicitly introduced for plants [178]. More recently,
607 Anzalone et al. (2021) introduced twin prime editing, where two pegRNAs are
608 introduced into the cell to create a more significant deletion in the DNA and replace the
609 deleted fragment with the introduced new fragment [179]. This technique has already
610 been shown to work in rice and may be the future gold standard for plant GE [180].

611 In addition to all the Cas9 toolkits already described, new Cas enzyme variants can be
612 identified from other organisms with various characteristics like cleavage efficiency,
613 minimal off-target cleavage, or expanded PAM sequence requirements [181–183].

614 Cas12 only needs the protospacer or crRNA to locate the target and cleaves
615 approximately 20 bp before the PAM sequence, while Cas13 targets only ssRNA
616 instead of DNA [184–186]. Cas12 and Cas14a1 have a *trans*-cleavage ability, opening
617 the possibility to cut nonspecific ssDNA [187,188]. Besides targeting single or multiple
618 genes, implementing the CRISPR/Cas system for chromosome engineering is being
619 discussed [176,189]. This system enables the transfer of whole chromosome arms
620 containing the desired QTLs into cultivars of interest in the breeding pipeline [189]. The
621 first demonstration of chromosome engineering was recently performed in maize [190].

622 3.2. Diminishing effects: How to solve hurdles of pleiotropic effects.

623 In most cases, the mutation of S genes causes unpredicted phenotypes due to their
624 involvement in multiple physiological processes. The consequences of S gene
625 inactivation could be fitness costs [191,192], impact on beneficial microbes [193,194] or
626 susceptibility to other pathogens [195–198]. To incorporate S genes for resistance
627 breeding, the pleiotropic effects of their inactivation should be avoided or minimised. To
628 this end, classical mutation breeding has resolved some of these pleiotropic effects by
629 selecting suitable genotypes or mild S gene alleles. However, in the last decade, NGTs
630 have enabled the introduction of targeted changes in the S genes and minimised the
631 pleiotropic effects associated with the changes in the S genes [199]. For instance,
632 developing a CRISPR/Cas9-based multiplex GE system enabled the simultaneous
633 knockout of multiple S gene alleles and trade-off genes. This approach is also helpful for
634 editing redundant genes in hybrid and polyploid genomes. For instance, the
635 simultaneous inactivation of the MLO homoalleles in the three sub-genomes of
636 hexaploidy wheat was necessary for powdery mildew resistance [86]. Moreover,
637 modifying the three TaEDR1 homoeologous enhanced powdery mildew resistance in
638 wheat [200].

639 Abolishing of the TALE effectors' binding sites in the target S genes has been
640 considered for improving resistance and reducing pleiotropy. A multiplex CRISPR/Cas9-
641 mediated GE approach obliterated the potential TALE binding sites within the promoters

642 of three SWEET genes that successfully improved broad-spectrum resistance of
643 bacterial blight in rice without any trade-offs [201]. The edited rice plants didn't show any
644 defects in the agronomic performances. In addition to the standard CRISPR/Cas9
645 procedures, base editing has also assisted in precisely modifying S gene alleles to
646 improve host resistance. For instance, base editing of the eIF4E gene has generated
647 the natural eIF4E allele by a single base change that resulted in loss of susceptibility
648 against potyviruses without any pleiotropic effects [202]. In addition to the TALE effector
649 binding sites, the miRNA binding sites can be targeted to modulate miRNA binding and
650 S gene regulation. In this regard, nematode-inducible miR827-mediated silencing of
651 NLA can be approached by introducing a silent mutation in the NLA gene using base or
652 primer editing [134]. This approach can be exploited to abandon the post-transcriptional
653 silencing of NLA, thereby improving the host immune responses and limiting the
654 progression of diseases. Likewise, GE can also introduce or abolish promoter-residing
655 Cis-regulatory elements involved in the tissue-specific expression of S genes. In this
656 approach, the loss of function mutation of S genes could be limited to a specific tissue
657 or condition, resulting in improved S gene-mediated host resistance and minimising the
658 trade-offs of S gene mutation. In the case of multi-target effectors such as SnTox3,
659 simultaneous modification of the interacting modules is required for optimal pathogen
660 resistance [115,116].

661 In general, before designing any possible knockouts or modifications of S genes, it is
662 vital to know the physiological roles of the target S gene, identify its interacting trade-off
663 genes, and uncover the pathogen molecules and their mode of S gene regulation.
664 These approaches could assist in incorporating S genes into breeding programs without
665 adverse pleiotropic effects.

666 3.3. Overcome susceptibility: Generating new immunity traits.

667 Different approaches could be applied to create new immunity traits. A straightforward
668 approach would be transferring already described S gene-mediated resistance from one
669 species to another. For example, the resistance obtained by the STP3 knock-out

670 against *Pst* could also be used against other biotrophic fungal pathogens in different
671 species. Likewise, the resistance conferred by Tsn1 can also be exploited in other crop
672 species for controlling pathogens relying on the ToxA effector (Supplementary Table). In
673 the future, our understanding of protein function and validation of host-pathogen and
674 effector-S gene interaction will rapidly increase due to the recent advances in different
675 computational methods and power (machine learning and large language models) and
676 protein structure analysis (AlphaFold). Thus, researchers can employ these tools to
677 understand S gene interaction modules and identify and modulate protein motifs
678 required by pathogen effectors, thereby improving resistance. This approach has
679 already been successfully implemented to control Xoo in rice. The Xoo effector, AvrXa7,
680 targets the promoter of *OsSWEET14* and remodelling of the effector binding promoter
681 region of *OsSWEET14* via base editing conferred resistance against the pathogen
682 [203]. NLRs are the targets of modification for obtaining resistance against pathogens.
683 In this regard, developing novel NLRs (RGA5) by modifying its heavy metal-associated
684 domain confers resistance against *M. oryzae* in transgenic rice [204]. Furthermore, the
685 engineering of RGA5 by integrating a decoy domain has been examined for an
686 extended recognition of effectors and improved resistance [205]. However, the results
687 revealed that the modification did not confer extended disease resistance against *M.*
688 *oryzae* in rice [205].

689 We believe that NGTs could aid protein modification and miRNA blocking in the S genes
690 for generating resistant cultivars (Fig. 3). The modification of the S gene protein could
691 be performed to block either interaction site for effector or interacting host protein
692 conferring susceptibility while maintaining protein function (Fig. 3). For instance, in the
693 RipI-GADs interaction module, modification of the GADs abolishes the binding of RipI
694 that would stop calmodulin binding and activation while maintaining the physiological
695 function of GADs (Fig. 2 and 3). In addition, modifying the miRNA172 binding site in
696 TOE1 avoids the miRNA172 binding that would allow FT repression and confer
697 resistance to *M. javanica*. However, since auxins control miRNA172, the modification of
698 TOE1 needs to be fine-tuned, which would partially reduce the TOE1 activity. In contrast

699 to silencing miRNAs, the modulation of miRNA binding sites in the target genes
700 maintains the regulatory roles of the miRNA, as most miRNAs interact with more than
701 one gene. Recently, the 20-nucleotide modification of an endogenous maize miRNA
702 (zma-MIR166h) targets a chitinase gene in the European corn borer pest but also
703 imposes unwanted impacts on non-target organisms [206]. In summary, the
704 development of new genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, and computational tools
705 provides excellent platforms for identifying and functionally validating more S genes
706 against various plant pathogens.

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708 Conflict of Interests

709 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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714 Figures

715 Fig. 1. Sunburst diagram of the list of S genes and the corresponding pathogens in
716 Arabidopsis and wheat plant species. Under the S gene category for both Arabidopsis
717 and wheat, the type of pathogens, lifestyle of the pathogens and the biological function
718 of the S genes are described in separate layers with distinct colours. The layers, from
719 inside to outside, are in the order of plant species, S gene category, pathogen group,
720 pathogen lifecycle, and S gene function. The figure was created using Python and
721 Plotly, and all the required packages are listed in the supplement.

722 Fig. 2. Schematic overview of representative S genes and their involvement in plant
723 susceptibility against the relevant pathogens. Selected S genes with distinct modes of
724 regulation against specific pathogens are described as pathogen entry and sustenance,
725 suppression of defence and nutrient acquisition categories. The interactions of the
726 pathogen effectors/molecules and S genes are shown with arrows and flat-end arrows
727 to indicate the activating/ inducing and negative/deactivating functions. The shields
728 represent the activation (green) or suppression (red) plant defence responses. The
729 figure was created using the BioRender software (www.biorender.com).

730 Fig. 3. Schematic overview of current NGTs and potential use of the techniques for S
731 gene modification. The figure was created using the BioRender software
732 (www.biorender.com).

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